

D6.4 FINAL DISSEMINATION REPORT

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

JOIN THE MISSION TO BE BETTER PREPARED FOR FUTURE CROSS-BORDER HEALTH THREATS

Representing 24 countries in Europe, UNITED4Surveillance gathers expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data-science to support the strengthening of integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control on national and European level

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

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1. Executive summary

The final dissemination report summarises the communication and dissemination activities implemented during the UNITED4Surveillance Joint Action, based on the consolidated partner dataset dated 19 June 2026. The report shows that dissemination was not a single central activity, but a consortium-wide effort implemented through many national, professional and European channels.

The updated dataset contains 441 retained activity records: 169 communication activities and 272 dissemination activities. Activity increased substantially in the second reporting period, with 295 records compared with 146 in the first reporting period. This development reflects the natural progress of the project from initial visibility and stakeholder engagement towards wider sharing of outputs, tools, pilot experiences and lessons learned.

The activities covered a broad mix of channels, including websites, social media, newsletters, press and media outputs, meetings, workshops, trainings, conferences, reports, scientific outputs and direct stakeholder engagement. In addition, 167 records include links and 280 records contain information on how many people were reached.

Based on these results, we conclude that the overall picture is positive. Partners made visible and sustained efforts to communicate the purpose of UNITED4Surveillance, engage relevant audiences and disseminate project results. Their contributions helped connect the project with public health authorities, laboratories, epidemiologists, researchers, healthcare professionals, policy stakeholders and wider audiences, thereby strengthening the practical value and future uptake of the project results.

2. Description of task

Report on the total of dissemination and communication activities executed during the JA.

This final report provides a consolidated overview of reported communication and dissemination activities during the project implementation period. It brings together partner inputs from the first and second reporting periods and presents the main achievements, results, and conclusions in a concise narrative format supported by summary tables and charts.

The purpose of the report is not only to document the number of activities carried out, but also to show how information about UNITED4Surveillance was disseminated within the consortium and reached key professional, policy and public audiences. It therefore highlights how consortium partners have driven the project's visibility, knowledge exchange, and dissemination of outputs.

3. Description of work & main achievements

3.1 Background of the task

UNITED4Surveillance brings together expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data science to strengthen integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control at national and European level. Communication and dissemination activities are essential to this objective, as they support visibility of the project, stakeholder engagement, transfer of knowledge and uptake of project outputs by public health authorities, professional communities and wider audiences.

From the start of the project, dissemination activities had to serve several complementary purposes: i) to explain the objectives of the project, ii) to inform national and European stakeholders about ongoing work, iii) to create opportunities for exchange between experts, and iv) to make emerging outputs visible beyond individual work packages. This required both central coordination and active implementation by partners in their own institutional and national settings.

The reported activities demonstrate that partners used their existing institutional channels and professional networks to reach the audiences that are most relevant to their work. This is a major strength of the dissemination approach: information about the project did not remain within the consortium, but was channelled through national websites, stakeholder meetings, professional newsletters, workshops, trainings, scientific events, reports and social media. As a result, project information was shared through trusted channels already used by public health communities.

The dissemination activities were carried out throughout the project by consortium partners at both national and European level. Activities were adapted to the nature of each work package and national context, ranging from broad public information and web visibility to targeted expert meetings, scientific outputs, trainings and presentations of pilot study results. This combination helped increase the relevance, credibility and sustainability of the project results.

3.2 Description of the work carried out

The work carried out consisted of collecting, consolidating, and reviewing partner-reported communication and dissemination activities during two reporting periods. The updated consolidated workbook was used as the primary source for this final narrative report.

In this report, communication activities are understood as strategically planned actions aimed at promoting the project, its objectives and results throughout the project lifetime, while dissemination activities are understood as specific project-related actions aimed at sharing project outputs, knowledge or materials with relevant target groups and stakeholders.

Scientific outputs related to the project were also reviewed as part of the final dissemination evidence. To keep the main narrative report concise, these outputs are presented separately in Annex 1, which provides an overview of publications, conference contributions and posters linked to the project work packages. The annex complements the consolidated activity dataset by showing how project results were also disseminated through scientific and professional channels.

The consolidation work was coordinated centrally, but the substance of the deliverable is based on partner contributions. Partners reported activities implemented through their organisations, national systems and work package networks. Their inputs demonstrate practical engagement with dissemination obligations and show how different institutions contributed according to their roles, expertise and stakeholder environments.

- Partner inputs were merged into a single activity dataset and categorised as communication or dissemination.
- Activities were reviewed by reporting period, country or partner label, organisation, type or channel, target audience, status, links and comments.
- Where reach figures were provided, they were retained as contextual evidence; however, they were not aggregated into a single total number, because partners used different metrics, such as participants, views, impressions, website reach, and general audience estimates.
- The narrative assessment focuses on activity volume, diversity of channels, audiences reached, evidence of partner engagement, and the contribution of dissemination activities to the sustainability of project results.

The consolidated activities demonstrate that partners used a broad and complementary mix of communication channels. National websites and project pages supported ongoing visibility; meetings, workshops and trainings enabled knowledge exchange with professionals and authorities; conferences and scientific outputs helped position the work within expert communities; and social media and newsletters supported wider awareness of selected outputs.

This partner-driven approach increased the value of our dissemination activities. Activities were not limited to formal reporting requirements; they supported dialogue, practical learning, stakeholder involvement, and the gradual transfer of project outputs into national and European professional communities.

3.3 Results

The consolidated dataset includes a total of 441 retained communication and dissemination activities. Dissemination activities form the larger share of the dataset (272; 62%), while communication activities account for 169 records (38%).

Table 1. Key indicators from the consolidated activity dataset

Indicator	Value
Total retained communication and dissemination activities	441
Communication activities	169 (38%)
Dissemination activities	272 (62%)
First reporting period activities	146
Second reporting period activities	295
Records with some quantitative reach indication	280 (63%)

Table 2 presents the reported communication and dissemination activities by category and reporting period.

Table 2. Activities by category and reporting period

Category	First reporting period	Second reporting period	Total
Communication	57	112	169
Dissemination	89	183	272
Total	146	295	441

Table 3 summarises the distribution of reported activities by communication and dissemination method group across the two reporting periods.

Table 3. Activities by communication and dissemination channel group

Channel group	Activities	First period	Second period
Events, conferences, workshops and meetings	261	80	181
Other / partner-specific activity	67	15	52
Social media	31	10	21
Websites and web portals	24	22	2
Newsletters and bulletins	21	7	14
Reports, publications and scientific outputs	22	7	15
Media and press	7	1	6
Training and education	4	4	0
Cross-project collaboration	4	0	4

In the consolidated dataset, the largest group of activities was events, conferences, workshops and meetings, indicating that reported communication and dissemination relied strongly on direct professional interaction. Websites, newsletters, social media and media outputs complemented these activities by supporting broader visibility and access to project information.

The number of activities varied across partner and country labels, reflecting different national context and reporting practices. Reported activities addressed a wide range of audiences, including national and regional public health authorities, ministries, laboratories, epidemiologists, healthcare professionals, researchers, industry partners, EU and international stakeholders, and the general public. Examples in the dataset include national project webpages, public and professional newsletters, stakeholder workshops, presentations on work from the One Health and Hospital surveillance work package, training and knowledge-exchange meetings on outbreak detection tools, conference contributions, LinkedIn posts, and closing-meeting dissemination of project outcomes.

This diversity of audiences shows that the project information moved through several layers: from internal project work to national professional networks, from expert and policy discussions to wider institutional communication channels, and from pilot outputs to scientific and professional communities. This multi-layered dissemination pathway is one of the main strengths of the project.

Table 4. How dissemination activities supported project value

Dissemination pathway	Contribution to project value
Sustained project visibility	Project pages, websites, social media posts, newsletters and updates for wider audiences kept UNITED4Surveillance visible throughout the implementation period and made basic project information accessible beyond the consortium.
Stakeholder engagement	National and European meetings, workshops, round tables and conferences brought together public health authorities, laboratories, epidemiologists, policy stakeholders and other expert audiences.
Knowledge transfer and capacity building	Training, educational events and technical exchanges supported practical understanding of integrated surveillance, outbreak detection, laboratory data

	transfer, One Health approaches and Hospital surveillance.
Dissemination of outputs and lessons learned	Partners shared pilot experiences, tools, methods, scientific outputs, reports and conference contributions, helping the results move from project work packages into professional communities.
Sustainability of results	Ongoing web resources, professional networks, cross-project collaboration and closing-period dissemination activities created a stronger basis for continued uptake after the reporting period.

In addition to the consolidated overview of communication and dissemination activities, Annex 1 provides a complementary overview of scientific outputs linked to the project, including published, submitted and planned publications, conference contributions and posters. These outputs further demonstrate how UNITED4Surveillance results and lessons learned were disseminated within scientific and professional communities, supporting the wider visibility, credibility and sustainability of the Joint Action.

3.4 Evaluation and conclusions

The dissemination and communication work can be evaluated positively on the basis of the consolidated partner reporting dataset. The updated data show broad partner involvement, a diverse mix of communication and dissemination methods, and a clear increase in activity as the project moved from establishment and awareness-raising towards dissemination of concrete outputs and lessons learned.

The increase in dissemination activities in the second reporting period can be interpreted as reflecting the later phase of the project, when more outputs, pilot results and implementation experiences had become available for sharing.

These results should be interpreted together with the qualitative content of the records. The value of the activities is not only reflected in their number, but also in their diversity: partners used different methods for different audiences, from public web information to highly targeted professional discussions and scientific dissemination.

The dataset shows a complementary use of communication and dissemination methods. Communication activities helped keep the project visible and accessible, while dissemination activities supported the exchange of more specialised outputs with target audiences from public health, laboratory, epidemiology, policy and research fields.

A key project benefit is that partners reported activities directed at stakeholder groups that are expected to use, further disseminate or build on the results. Partners did not rely only on central project communication. They used national institutional websites, professional meetings, workshops, scientific events, newsletters, social media and expert networks to reach these stakeholder groups through established institutional and professional routes. This supports continued visibility and potential uptake of project knowledge, tools and lessons after the formal reporting period.

The partner contributions also demonstrate good collaboration across the consortium. The dataset includes activities implemented by individual partners, joint activities and cross-project exchanges. This indicates that dissemination was embedded in the wider technical work of the project and supported by cooperation between work packages, national institutes and European partners.

In conclusion, the communication and dissemination activities contributed meaningfully to project visibility, stakeholder engagement, knowledge exchange and sustainability. The final dataset provides evidence of strong, partner-driven dissemination efforts and a positive basis for continued use of UNITED4Surveillance outputs.

3.5 Data management

The report is based on administrative monitoring data provided by project partners for the purpose of documenting dissemination and communication activities.

The consolidated workbook was used as the working dataset. It retains key descriptive fields such as category, reporting period, date, country or partner label, organisation, activity name, channel, target audience, status, links and comments. These fields made it possible to describe not only the number of activities, but also the pathways through which project information was shared.

The dataset does not require personal data processing for the purpose of this report. Where partner-provided links and public references were included, they were treated as supporting evidence for the documented dissemination activities.

4. Deviations from the work plan

No deviations from the work plan were identified for the preparation of this deliverable.

5. Performance of the partners

Partner performance was strong overall, based on the consolidated dataset that demonstrates active participation across the consortium and partners' contributions through both national and international communication and dissemination methods. Contributions ranged from a high volume of communication and dissemination activities to more targeted activities addressing specific professional or policy audiences.

The active contribution of partners is one of the main positive findings of the report. Partners made visible efforts to communicate the project in their own environments, using trusted institutional channels and established professional networks. This helped ensure that information about UNITED4Surveillance was not limited to central project communication, but reached audiences that are directly relevant for surveillance practice and policy.

Partners contributed to the visibility and uptake of UNITED4Surveillance through project webpages, newsletters, social media, stakeholder workshops, expert meetings, trainings, scientific and professional events, reports and dissemination of pilot outputs. This diversity of activities strengthened the project's reach and supported knowledge exchange between public health institutes, laboratories, ministries, researchers and other relevant stakeholders.

Table 6. Main ways in which partners contributed to dissemination and project value

Partner contribution area	Observed contribution
High-volume and broad dissemination activity	Several partners reported substantial number of activities across communication and dissemination methods, showing sustained effort to keep stakeholders informed and engaged.
Targeted national implementation	Partners adapted dissemination to national contexts, including project webpages, professional newsletters, national stakeholder events, workshops and tailored exchanges with authorities and expert groups.
Scientific and professional visibility	Partners contributed to conferences, posters, journal submissions, reports and expert meetings, strengthening the credibility and technical visibility of the project.
Cross-border and cross-work-package collaboration	Joint and combined activities, cross-project collaboration and multi-partner meetings demonstrate that dissemination was not isolated, but supported the wider European surveillance community.
Coordination and transparency	The final consolidation was coordinated centrally, but its substance depended on the responsiveness, documentation and cooperation of partners across the consortium.

The data also show that partners contributed in different but complementary ways. Some focused strongly on conferences, workshops and meetings; others used websites, newsletters and social media to maintain visibility; and several partners contributed to scientific and professional outputs. This variation is positive because it reflects the different roles, contexts, expertise and stakeholder relationships within the consortium.

Overall, the performance of partners supports the conclusion that communication and dissemination were implemented as an integral part of the project. The partner-driven dissemination effort contributed positively to project visibility, practical knowledge exchange and the sustainability of project results.

Annex 1. Overview of scientific output (Milestone 54)

(Scientific) articles

1. Grøntvedt et al. Surveillance for Influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 in Swine and Humans in Norway. *In preparation*.
2. Jore S, Tonnessen R, Grøntvedt CA, Rydland K, Hauge AG, Hungnes O, Kristoffersen AB, Fossum E. A retrospective cross-sectional study (2009-2023): exploring influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 antibody time series in humans and swine and vaccine coverage in two target groups. *Zoonoses and Public Health*. 2026 March; 73:336-347. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/zph.70051>
3. Kerkvliet JJ, Stege PB, Coipan C, Lanzl M, van der Voort M, Mughini-Gras L, van der Weijden C, Kampfraath AA, Koene MGJ, van den Beld M, Pijnacker R, Franz E. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. *Submitted Eurosurveillance*.
4. Larose T et al. Navigating force Majeure in EU4Health Projects: lessons from Norway's government reorganisation. *In preparation*.
5. Marbus SD, Boer TM, Veldhuijzen IK, van Gageldonk-Lafeber AB. Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals: what's in it for us? *BMC Health Services Research*. 2026 April; 26: 731. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12913-026-14513-2>
6. Pijnacker R, van den Beld M, Ulrich A, Ceyskens PJ, van Cauteren D, Solveig Jore, Nielsen EM, Ethelberg S, Morabito S, Lanzl M, Franz E. Implementing whole genome sequencing for foodborne pathogen surveillance: insights and recommendations based on expert experiences. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 2025 Dec; 16: 1-8. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2025.1707621/abstract>
7. Sassu EL, Polzer D, Stätter M, Buzanich-Ladinig A, Klinger J, Leeb B, Wilhelm E, Cvjetkovic V, Schmolz F, Kpacka I, Revilla-Fernández S. Pilot multisectoral surveillance of swine influenza A virus in Austria reveals diverse lineages and potential human-to-swine H1N1pdm09 transmission. *In preparation*.
8. Torres-Ruesta A, Lehtonen T, Sane J, Leino T. Defining Severe Acute Respiratory Infection (SARI) hospitalisations in Finland: Evaluation of case definitions for register-based surveillance, 2021-2021. *In preparation*.
9. vom Felde genannt Imbush P et al. Collaborative development of open-source outbreak detection tools: Needs, concept and implementation. *Eur J Public Health*. 2024 Oct; 34: ckae144.1148. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckae144.1148>
10. vom Felde genannt Imbush P, Vietor AC, Markus I, Diercke M, Ullrich A. Automated outbreak detection systems in the EU: Requirements and challenges for its implementation, 2023-2024. *Under review JMIR Public Health Surveill*: Preprint available from: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.64898/2026.02.20.26346630v1.full>

(Poster) presentations

1. Galea N et al. Lessons learned : Building a Lab Based Gastrointestinal Surveillance System in Malta. Poster presented at: XI Malta Medical School Conference 2025; 4 Dec 2025; Valetta, Malta
2. Kairiene B et al. Presentation about UNITED4Surveillance and its activities during seminar INFODAY - information event to present the European Union Health Programme 2021-2027 "EU4HEALTH" (EU4HEALTH) and its Action Plan 2023; 11 April; Vilnius, Lithuania
3. Kairienė B. Fit for purpose surveillance – strategies to implement effective surveillance systems in EU/EEA countries under the new Serious Cross Border Health Threats Regulation (2022/2371). Conference presentation at: 16th European Public Health Conference; 10 Nov 2023; Dublin, Ireland
4. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at NVMM Scientific Spring Meeting; 30 March 2026; Arnhem, the Netherlands
5. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at: EOHA; 19 May 2026; Madrid.
6. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at: UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
7. Leino T et al. Development of Register-based surveillance of severe acute respiratory infection (SARI) hospitalizations in Finland. Poster submitted: ESCAIDE 2026.
8. Liptáková M et al. Project UNITED4Surveillance – Building Union and National capacities for integrated surveillance. Poster presented at: 31st Pečenka's Epidemiological Days; 11-13 Sept 2024; Plzeň, Czech Republic.
9. Marbus SD et al. Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals. Poster presented at UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
10. Masset H. Salmonella spp. as a be.Prepared case study for integration of health data as a way of strengthening preparedness for infectious diseases. Poster presented at: I3S conference, 23 June 2025; Saint-Malo, France
11. Melillo T et al. Strengthening Infectious disease Surveillance through Electronic Health Records and Automated Data Flows in Malta. Conference presentation at: 4th National Public Health Conference; 24-25 Nov 2023; Msida, Malta
12. Parys A. ZOOIS. Conference presentation at: 20205 SSID; 22 May; Brussels, Belgium
13. Sassu EL et al. Coordinated effort fort he surveillance of zoonotic influenza in Austria. Poster presented at: BeOH 2025; 22-23 Jan; Brussels, Belgium.
14. Sassu EL et al. Pilot multisectoral surveillance of swine influenza A virus in Austria reveals diverse lineages and potential human-to-swine H1N1pdm09 transmission. Poster submitted: ESFLU.
15. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening swine influenza surveillance in Austria through a multisectoral network: a pilot study from 2023-2025. Poster presented at: ESPHM 2026; 13-16 May, Florence, Italy.
16. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening swine influenza surveillance in Austria through a multisectoral network: a pilot study from 2023-2025. Poster presented at: UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
17. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening the communication between veterinary and medical authorities in the context of zoonotic influenza. Conference presentation at: OneH Congres 2026; 3-5 Jun; Saint-Quay-Portrieux; Brittany, France

18. Sciensano. ZOOIS: Zoonotische influenza surveillance bij varkensdierenartsen en varkens in België. Poster presented at: IPVS conference (International Pig Veterinary Society); 5 Dec 2025; Beveren, Belgium
19. Serdt M, Klepac P, Klavs I, Lejko Zupanc T, Logar M. UNITED4Surveillance – Union and national capacity building for integrated surveillance – Work package 3: hospital surveillance: surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to hospitalisation. Poster presented at: Slovenian National Conference on Public Health; 1-2 October 2024; Maribor, Slovenia.
20. SSI. "One Health - når mennesker og dyr smitter hinanden" (One Health – When Humans and Animals Infect Each Other), Presentation at: Nordic Infection Prevention and Control Conference; 14 April 2025; Gothenburg, Sweden
21. Stätter M. Main results of swine influenza surveillance in domestic pigs. Poster presented at: European Symposium of Porcine Health Management (ESPHM) 2025; 22 May; Bern, Switzerland
22. Van Dyck W. Major Salmonella Enteritidis outbreak linked to egg consumption. Conference presentation at: 2025 SSID; 22 May; Brussels, Belgium
23. Vietor AC. An open-source signal detection tool for infectious disease outbreaks: The development and application of signal detection methods within the European Public Health Community. Conference presentation at: DAGStat 2025 (German Working Group of Statistics); 24-28 April; Berlin, Germany.
24. Vietor AC. Collaborative development of a framework for automated signal detection for infectious disease outbreaks. Conference presentation at: 3rd (Inter-) National Conference on Infectious Disease Modeling 2025 (MONID); 26-28 Feb 2025; Berlin, Germany.
25. Vietor AC. Signal Detection Tool: An R shiny app supporting automated detection of infectious disease outbreaks. Conference presentation at: ShinyConf 2025; 9-11 April (online).
26. vom Felde genannt Imbush P et al. Collaborative development of open-source outbreak detection tools: Needs, concept and implementation. Poster presented at: 17th European Public Health Conference 2024; 12-15 Nov; Lisbon, Portugal.
27. WBVR. Poster presented at: Paradigm shifts for Global Oe Health; 24 April 2024; Wageningen, the Netherlands.
28. Witteveen-Freidl G et al. Lessons learnt from a One Health stakeholder analysis and systems mapping workshop on avian and swine influenza surveillance in humans in Denmark. Poster session presented at: ESCAIDE 2024; 20-22 Nov; Stockholm, Sweden.

Reports

1. WP2 - Task 1 report: [Legal challenges with respect to lab-data sharing in the EU/ EEA](#)
2. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Denmark](#)
3. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Finland](#)
4. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Norway](#)
5. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [the Netherlands](#)
6. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Denmark](#)
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24. WP4: Pilot report - [Austria - F. tularensis](#)
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28. WP4: Pilot report - [Denmark - STEC](#)
29. WP4: Pilot report - [Denmark - zoonotic influenza](#)
30. WP4: Pilot report - [Italy - Shiga toxin-producing E. coli \(STEC\)](#)
31. WP4: Pilot report - [Lithuania - Salmonella](#)
32. WP4: Pilot report - [Lithuania - Tick-borne Encephalitis \(TBE\)](#)
33. WP4: Pilot report - [the Netherlands - Salmonella & Campylobacter | UNITED4Surveillance](#)
34. WP4: Pilot report - [Spain - West Nile virus \(WNV\) | UNITED4Surveillance](#)

Deliverable reports

1. D1.1 Progress report
2. D1.2 Project booklet
3. D2.1 Review existing lab surveillance systems and outbreak detection systems
4. D2.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for improved lab-based reporting and outbreak detection
5. D3.1 Report on MS survey and piloting plans
6. D3.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for digitalized surveillance systems of severe infectious diseases
7. D4.1 Inventarisation goals, stakeholders and One Health surveillance systems
8. D4.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for implementing One Health surveillance
9. D5.1 Report on evaluation workshop
10. D5.2 Final evaluation report
11. D6.1 Project website
12. D6.2 UNITED4Surveillance infographic
13. D6.3 Initial assessment MS surveillance systems and needs assessment
14. D6.4 Final dissemination report
15. D7.1 Baseline report national sustainability plans
16. D7.2 Progress report on national sustainability plans implementation
17. D7.3 Final report: Roadmap to implementation of integration infectious diseases surveillance